

Data Management Plan

Analyzing Airbnb and its impact in Vienna

Contact person

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Based on

Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.0.1 (dsw:root:2.0.1)

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Abstract

Airbnb in Vienna is far from the air bed that gave the company its name. Thousands of apartments have been converted from long-term rental units into accommodations for tourists. This leads to rising rents and changing neighborhoods. This experiment should show how many apartments are listed on Airbnb and how many of them are considered active.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Re-used datasets

We will use the following reference datasets:

- **InsideAirbnb / Vienna March 2020** (<http://insideairbnb.com/get-the-data.html>)

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **CSV**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

PNG

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2. How will the data be collected or created?

There will be no instrument dataset in this project.

Storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders. We have made appointments about naming the files.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will use a relational database system to store project data. We will be allowing Create, Update and Delete operations for data in the database.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use other solution than (electronic) lab notebooks to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis: Dockerfile.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **InsideAirbnb** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). All project web services addressed via secure http (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The risk of information leak in the project or organization is acceptably low. We will mitigate information vandalism risk for the project or organization.

All personal data will be collected anonymously.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- [Active Apartments on Airbnb in Vienna March 2020](#) – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible. – The metadata will be available even when the data no longer exists.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- [Active Apartments on Airbnb in Vienna March 2020](#) – will be stored in a domain-specific repository: [Zenodo](#). We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- [Active Apartments on Airbnb in Vienna March 2020](#) – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Christoph Kiss is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute. To run the DMP, check out the following repository and run the docker file in it: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737914>

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.